

Adaptive FM-OFDM for 6G Non-Terrestrial Networks

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Abstract—The integration of non-terrestrial networks (NTNs) into the 3GPP mobile communications standards is key to enabling global coverage and ubiquity to fulfill the demanding scenarios upcoming for the sixth generation (6G). However, satellite systems suffer from challenges such as large Doppler shifts, nonlinear distortion from high power amplifiers (HPAs) and phase noise, which degrade the performance of the existing fifth generation (5G) new radio (NR) waveform, orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM). Recently, frequency-modulated OFDM (FM-OFDM) has emerged as a robust alternative suitable for high-mobility and phase noise while maintaining a constant envelope to handle nonlinear distortions. However, FM-OFDM suffers from large variations in the subcarrier signal-to-noise ratios (SNRs), which can lead to sub-optimal performance. In this work, we present an adaptive FM-OFDM using a bit loading technique in order to maximize data rates for a target bit error rate (BER). We demonstrate through performance evaluations that our proposed FM-OFDM system outperforms state-of-the-art alternatives, particularly under challenging conditions such as HPA nonlinear effects, high Doppler shifts, and phase noise. Furthermore, we show that FM-OFDM meets the different requirements without requiring channel estimation or equalization, thereby simplifying receiver implementation and confirming its suitability for future 6G NTNs.

Index Terms—FM-OFDM, 6G, NTN, satellite, waveform

I. INTRODUCTION

Satellites can augment the fifth generation (5G) of mobile communication networks by extending coverage and addressing challenging use cases that ground-based infrastructure cannot reach. The integration of non-terrestrial networks (NTNs) into the Third Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) 5G new radio (NR) standard is crucial for paving the way to sixth generation (6G) networks, which will demand even more complex scenarios and continuous ubiquity [1].

However, satellite systems face several challenges, including large Doppler shifts (particularly in low orbits), nonlinear distortion introduced by high-power amplifiers (HPAs), and phase noise. These impairments are more severe in high frequency bands, degrading the performance of the current 5G NR waveform, i.e., orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM), due to its sensitivity to intercarrier interference (ICI) caused by Doppler shifts and phase noise, and its high peak-to-average power ratio (PAPR), which leads to distortion in the presence of HPAs.

As a result, state-of-the-art research is focused on finding suitable waveforms for 6G [2], [3]. Many of these studies are based on flexible architectures that are compatible with current

OFDM systems but introduce modifications to support high-mobility, lower PAPR and phase noise.

Recently, frequency-modulated-OFDM (FM-OFDM) has been proposed as a potential solution [4], demonstrating robustness to the impairments that might be caused by high-mobility and phase noise, while also maintaining a constant envelope suitable for handling the nonlinear distortions introduced by HPAs. Additionally, FM-OFDM has a significant advantage in flat-frequency channels, as it requires no channel estimation or equalization when the channels have large coherence bandwidths compared to the signal bandwidth [4]. This feature simplifies receiver implementations, which is particularly beneficial in NTNs, which usually have line-of-sight (LOS) conditions, especially at high frequencies. Therefore, we identify the FM-OFDM as a strong candidate for 6G NTNs. Nonetheless, to the best of our knowledge, no prior research has investigated its application in NTN scenarios.

Despite all these benefits, FM-OFDM experiences significant variations in subcarrier signal-to-noise ratios (SNRs) due to the frequency modulation, resulting in suboptimal performance and inefficient spectrum utilization. Therefore, in this work, we propose an adaptive FM-OFDM using a bit loading algorithm to maximize the throughput under a target bit error rate (BER). We show that this approach is crucial to obtain the full potential of FM-OFDM in NTNs.

Specifically, our contributions include the following:

- We propose an adaptive FM-OFDM through the use of a bit loading algorithm to ensure maximum throughput under a BER constraint. Results show that this algorithm is essential to efficiently utilize the spectrum due to the characteristics of the FM-OFDM waveform.
- We present a comparative study of the FM-OFDM waveform for NTNs alongside other potential waveform candidates. The study includes the following:
 - A comparative study of the total degradation (TD), or figure of merit [5]–[7], to evaluate the impact of the nonlinear HPA on BER performance, considering its operating point, specifically the input back-off (IBO) and output back-off (OBO).
 - We evaluate the performance of FM-OFDM for the link between a low Earth orbit (LEO) satellite and a ground user equipment (UE), comparing it with other potential waveform candidates for 6G. The

assessment includes considerations of the effects of Doppler shifts due to satellite movement, HPA nonlinearities and phase noise.

The results show that FM-OFDM achieves the required performance without channel estimation or equalization. We demonstrate its suitability for NTN, particularly when compared to the current 5G waveform, namely, cyclic prefix-OFDM (CP-OFDM), which becomes nearly impractical due to its high sensitivity to residual frequency offsets. Furthermore, we discuss the advantages over orthogonal time frequency space (OTFS) [8], a leading 6G waveform candidate, highlighting FM-OFDM's superior performance under HPA nonlinearities and lower complexity. This work emphasizes the potential of FM-OFDM in enhancing the performance and reliability of next-generation NTNs.

The paper is organized as follows. Section II introduces the system model. Section III describes the proposed adaptive FM-OFDM. Then, Section IV presents the comparative study and results; and, Section V concludes this work.

Notation: in this work, matrices, vectors and scalar quantities are represented by boldface uppercase, boldface lowercase, and normal letters, respectively. $[\mathbf{a}]_n$ is the n -th element of the vector \mathbf{a} . The superscripts $(\cdot)^T, (\cdot)^H$ and $(\cdot)^*$ denote transpose, hermitian and complex conjugate operations, respectively. $\Re(\cdot)$ and $\Im(\cdot)$ represent the real and imaginary part, respectively. $*$ denotes the convolution operation. $CN(0, \sigma^2)$ is the circularly-symmetric and zero-mean complex normal distribution with variance σ^2 . $\mathbb{C}^K, \mathbb{R}^K$ and \mathbb{Z}^K are K -dimensional complex, real and integer spaces, respectively, and $\mathbb{C}^{K \times K}$ is the $K \times K$ -dimensional complex space.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

A bidirectional radio link is considered between a ground UE and a satellite. At the transmitter, a FM-OFDM waveform is generated as follows [4]. A complex data vector is transmitted at the k -th FM-OFDM symbol ($k = 0, 1, \dots, K-1$), defined as $\mathbf{x}_k \in \mathbb{C}^{N_a}$, where N_a denotes the number of active subcarriers. The vector satisfies conjugate-symmetry condition, i.e.

$$\mathbf{x}_k = [0, [\mathbf{d}_k]_1 \dots [\mathbf{d}_k]_{N_s}, 0, [\mathbf{d}_k]_{N_s}^* \dots [\mathbf{d}_k]_1]^T, \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{d}_k \in \mathbb{C}^{N_s}$ is the complex data vector containing quadrature amplitude modulation (QAM) data symbols, whose energy is normalized to one ($\mathbb{E}\{[\mathbf{d}]_i^2\} = 1, 1 \leq i \leq N_s$), with $N_a = 2N_s + 2$. The vector is symmetrically zero-padded until size N , where N is a power of two and denotes the discrete Fourier transform (DFT) size. As a result, the output of the inverse DFT (IDFT) yields a real-valued signal

$$\mathbf{f}_k = \mathbf{F}_N^H \mathbf{x}_k \in \mathbb{R}^N, \quad k = 0, 1, \dots, K-1, \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{F}_N \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times N}$ is the normalized DFT matrix. Then, a frequency modulator block generates the instantaneous phase signal through an accumulator, which afterwards passes through a phase modulator

$$[\mathbf{r}_k]_n = \sum_{i=1}^n [\mathbf{f}_k]_i \in \mathbb{R}^N, \quad [\mathbf{c}_k]_n = e^{j2\pi m[\mathbf{r}_k]_n} \in \mathbb{C}^N, \quad (3)$$

where n is the time sample index $n = 1, \dots, N$, m denotes the modulation index, and \mathbf{c}_k has a constant envelope $|\mathbf{c}_k|_n = 1$. A zero-padding (ZP) of length L_{ZP} is appended to every FM-OFDM symbol yielding the transmitted signal $\mathbf{s} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_T K}$, with $N_T = N + L_{ZP}$, as the concatenation of the vectors at every k -th FM-OFDM symbol. At the transmitter, a HPA introduces nonlinear distortions, as described later.

The signal goes through a multipath and time varying channel, yielding the received signal $\mathbf{y} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_T K}$

$$\mathbf{y} = (\mathbf{h} * \mathbf{s}) e^{j\phi_n} + \mathbf{w}, \quad [\mathbf{y}]_n = \left(\sum_{\tau=1}^{L_\tau} [\mathbf{h}]_\tau [\mathbf{s}]_{n-\tau+1} \right) e^{j\phi} + [\mathbf{w}]_n, \quad (4)$$

where $\mathbf{w} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_T K}$ represents the additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN) whose distribution is given by $CN(0, \sigma_z^2)$, $\mathbf{h} \in \mathbb{C}^{L_{CH}}$ is the channel impulse response of L_{CH} taps with $L_\tau = L_{CH}$ for $n \geq L_{CH}$ and $L_\tau = n$ for $n < L_{CH}$, and the complex exponential $e^{j\phi_n}$ with a time-varying phase ϕ_n denotes the phase noise.

At the receiver, channel estimation and equalization are performed only if necessary. Therefore, if needed, piecewise equalization is considered in this work [9], which yields the received vector $\hat{\mathbf{c}}_k \in \mathbb{C}^N$. The phase is extracted according to

$$[\hat{\mathbf{r}}_k]_n = \frac{1}{2\pi m} \arctan \left(\frac{\Im([\hat{\mathbf{c}}_k]_n)}{\Re([\hat{\mathbf{c}}_k]_n)} \right) \in \mathbb{R}^N. \quad (5)$$

A phase unwrapper [10] is used to deal with phase ambiguities provoked by excursions out of the $(-\pi, \pi)$ range, and, after this, the frequency extraction is performed

$$[\hat{\mathbf{f}}_k]_q = \begin{cases} [\hat{\mathbf{r}}_q] & \text{for } q = 1 \\ [\hat{\mathbf{r}}_q] - [\hat{\mathbf{r}}_{q-1}] & \text{for } q > 1 \end{cases}, \quad (6)$$

followed by the DFT operation, yielding

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_k = \mathbf{F}_N \hat{\mathbf{f}}_k \in \mathbb{C}^N, \quad (7)$$

where the N_s data symbols $\hat{\mathbf{d}}_k$ can be demapped from the subcarriers.

III. PROPOSED ADAPTIVE FM-OFDM

In this section, we describe the proposed adaptive FM-OFDM waveform. As stated in [4], the SNR for FM-OFDM in an AWGN channel without impairments for the k -th FM-OFDM symbol can be approximated with the expression

$$SNR_k^{FM(Th)} = \frac{8\pi^2 m^2 N}{N_a \left(1 - \cos\left(\frac{2\pi q}{N}\right)\right)} SNR_{in}^{FM}, \quad (8)$$

where $q = 0, 1, \dots, N-1$ denotes the subcarrier index and SNR_{in} is the input SNR, which is defined as a function of an input bit energy-to-noise ratio E_b/N_0 as

$$\frac{E_b}{N_0} = SNR_{in} \frac{N}{N_u K_{QAM}}, \quad (9)$$

where N_u refers to the useful subcarriers ($N_u = N_a/2$ for FM-OFDM), and $K_{QAM} = \log_2(M)$ is the number of bits per symbol for a M-QAM. This is, for FM-OFDM

$$\frac{E_b}{N_0}^{FM} = SNR_{in}^{FM} \frac{2N}{N_a K_{QAM}}. \quad (10)$$

The expression in (8) is perceived as a monotonically decreasing function along the subcarriers, indicating that FM-OFDM inherently attains a higher SNR at the lowest subcarriers and gradually decays to significantly lower values [4]. The large variation in subcarrier SNRs leads to suboptimal performance when a fixed-size QAM is assigned to all subcarriers within an FM-OFDM symbol. Therefore, drawing on Chow's bit loading method [11], we propose a bit loading scheme for assigning the optimal number of bits per symbol per subcarrier, aiming to maximize throughput while maintaining a target BER.

The bit-loading algorithm involves the following steps:

1. **Obtain SNR Measurements:** Measure the SNRs $[SNR_k^{FM}]_q$ for $q = 1, \dots, N_s$. The theoretical approximation $SNR_k^{FM(Th)}$ in (8) is valid and could obviate the necessity for SNR estimation in AWGN channels and low modulation indices m , although the monotonic behavior remains similar when other impairments are present, especially in NTN, which commonly have LOS.
2. **Sort SNR Values:** Sort the $[SNR_k^{FM}]_q$ in descending order, ensuring that $[SNR_k^{FM}]_j \geq [SNR_k^{FM}]_{j+1}$ for $j = 1, \dots, N_s$. This step is generally not needed since the function is already monotonically decreasing in these scenarios. Then, the complexity of the algorithm can be further reduced by skipping it.
3. **Initialize variables:** Set $l = 1$, $b_{max} = 0$, and $B = 0$.
4. **Compute bits per subcarrier:** For each subcarrier up to the l -th, calculate the number of bits per subcarrier using:

$$[b_k]_j = \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{\varepsilon_{total} [SNR_k^{FM}]_j}{\Gamma} \right) \in \mathbb{R}, 1 \leq j \leq l, \quad (11)$$

where ε_{total} is the total signal energy, and Γ is the SNR gap for M-QAM, defined as [12]

$$\Gamma = \frac{1}{3} \left[Q^{-1} \left(\frac{SER}{4} \right) \right]^2. \quad (12)$$

Γ represents the difference between the capacity and the actual achievable rate, based on the desired target symbol error rate (SER), serving as a valid approximation that simplifies bit loading algorithms. The SER can be related to the BER through an approximation as $BER \approx SER/\log_2(M)$, particularly when Gray coding is used.

The bits per symbol in (11) are rounded to the nearest integer corresponding to 3GPP 5G NR possible modulation schemes, i.e. quadrature phase shift keying (QPSK), 16-QAM, 64-QAM or 256-QAM, yielding $[\bar{b}_k]_j \in \mathbb{Z}$. The total number of bits is computed as the sum of the previously computed bits as

$$[\bar{b}_{k,target}]_l = \sum_{j=1}^l [\bar{b}_k]_j. \quad (13)$$

Algorithm 1 Proposed bit loading for adaptive FM-OFDM

Input: N_s, ε_{TOTAL}

Output: Bits per symbol per subcarrier for the k -th FM-OFDM symbol, $[\bar{b}_k]_j$ for $j = 1, \dots, B$.

Initialization: $l = 1, b_{max} = 0, B = 0, stop = false$.

- 1: Obtain $[SNR_k^{FM}]_q, q = 1, \dots, N_s$ or use theoretical expression (8).
 - 2: Sort SNR $[SNR_k^{FM}]_j \geq [SNR_k^{FM}]_{j+1}$ for $j = 1, \dots, N_s$.
 - 3: **while** $stop == false$ **do**
 - 4: **for** $1 \leq j \leq l$ **do**
 - 5: Compute $[b_k]_j$ using (11)
 - 6: Round $[b_k]_j$ to closest 3GPP NR modulation.
 - 7: **end for**
 - 8: Compute total number of bits $[\bar{b}_{k,target}]_l$ using equation (13).
 - 9: **if** $[\bar{b}_{k,target}]_l > b_{max}$ **then**
 - 10: $[\bar{b}_{k,target}]_l = b_{max}$
 - 11: $B = l$
 - 12: **else**
 - 13: $stop = true$
 - 14: **end if**
 - 15: **if** $l \neq N_s$ **then**
 - 16: $l = l + 1$
 - 17: **end if**
 - 18: **end while**
 - 19: **return:** $[\bar{b}_k]_j$ for $j = 1, \dots, B$.
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5. **Update maximum bits:** If $[\bar{b}_{k,target}]_l > b_{max}$, update b_{max} to $[\bar{b}_{k,target}]_l$ and set $B = l$. The algorithm can stop here if $[\bar{b}_{k,target}]_l \leq b_{max}$.
6. **Iterate or terminate:** If $l \neq N_s$, then update $l = l + 1$ and return to step 4. Otherwise, the algorithm terminates with B indicating the optimal bandwidth (number of used subcarriers).

The number of bits per subcarrier corresponds to the bit distribution associated with the maximum $[\bar{b}_{k,target}]_l$ obtained in step 5, i.e. $[\bar{b}_k]_j$ for $j = 1, \dots, B$. The pseudocode can be found in Algorithm 1.

This bit loading algorithm is performed at the transmitter for each FM-OFDM symbol, where the $[\bar{b}_k]_j$ bits are modulated onto the N_s data subcarriers. These subcarriers are then mapped to \mathbf{x}_k as described in Section II.

The algorithm requires $B(B+1)/2$ total iterations due to the need to compute the bits per subcarrier up to l within each loop (B times). Consequently, the nested loops result in a computational complexity of up to $\mathcal{O}(B^2)$, where B has a maximum value of N_s . However, similarly to [11], adopting a binary-search to find b_{max} , instead of incrementing l one by one, significantly reduces the computational complexity of the algorithm to $\mathcal{O}(B \log(B))$.

IV. PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

This section presents the performance analysis and results of the proposed adaptive FM-OFDM system. In subsection

TABLE I
SIMULATION PARAMETERS

Parameter	Value
Carrier Frequency	Ka band: $f_{c,UL} = 30$ GHz, $f_{c,DL} = 20$ GHz
Modulation	QPSK, 16-QAM, 64-QAM, 256-QAM
Subcarrier spacing	$\Delta f = 120$ kHz.
Resource blocks (RBs)	25
Channel Model	NTN-TDLC5 (TS 38.101-5 Annex B)
Phase Noise	3GPP TR 38.803
HPA	TWTA (DL)
LEO Satellite Altitude	$h = 600$ km
Beam diameter	20 km
UE speed	Static VSAT ($v = 0$ km/h)
Elevation angle	$\theta = 50^\circ$

IV-A, the NTN scenario and simulation parameters are introduced. Subsequently, subsection IV-B demonstrates the effectiveness of the proposed bit loading technique. Subsection IV-C presents the total degradation, which is utilized to assess the performance of the FM-OFDM waveform in comparison with the state-of-the-art schemes under the nonlinear effects of a HPA. Ultimately, subsection IV-D presents a comparative study based on the BER performance between FM-OFDM and other 6G waveform candidates.

A. Satellite Scenario

The considered scenario follows the guidelines in 3GPP 38.821 [13]. The simulation parameters are the ones in Table I. We consider a LEO satellite link operating in the Ka band that connects with the ground UE, which is a static very-small-aperture terminal (VSAT). Both pre and post common Doppler shift compensations are considered. However, a residual frequency offset remains when the UE is not at the center of the beam. The UE performs synchronization in the downlink and estimates the frequency offset, namely $CFO_{DL} = CFO_1 + CFO_2$, where CFO_1 is due to the UE oscillator and CFO_2 accounts for the satellite movement [13]. In the uplink, the UE compensates the previously computed frequency offset, and, due to opposite signs of the Doppler shift in downlink and uplink, the total frequency offset at the uplink can be approximated to $CFO_{UL} \approx 2CFO_{DL}$. The exact computation of the maximum value of this residual frequency offset at the uplink after pre and post common Doppler shift compensation CFO_{UL}^{max} in Hz is given by the guidelines in Table 6.1.2-2 in 3GPP TR 38.821 [13]

$$CFO_{UL}^{max} = (DS_{sat} + DS_{UE} + 1)^2 (RO + 1) f_{c,UL} - f_{c,UL}, \quad (14)$$

where RO is the residual frequency offset after synchronization in Hz, DS_{sat} is the residual Doppler shift due to satellite movement in Hz after common Doppler compensation, DS_{UE} denotes the Doppler shift due to UE movement in Hz and $f_{c,UL}$ is the central frequency used on the service uplink in Hz. The values for these parameters are provided in Table 6.1.1-8 3GPP TR 38.821 [13]. HPA nonlinearities are primarily present in the downlink. In this work, the nonlinearity is

Fig. 1. Throughput gain for the proposed bit loading algorithm for FM-OFDM in an AWGN channel. Target BER of 10^{-5} .

Fig. 2. Throughput gain for the proposed bit loading algorithm for uplink FM-OFDM in NTN-TDLC5. Target BER of 10^{-4} .

modeled based on a traveling wave tube amplifier (TWTA), as described in [14].

B. Bit Loading

This subsection presents the results in terms of throughput gain for the proposed bit loading technique for FM-OFDM. In this work, we perform perfect SNR estimation [15]. Fig. 1 illustrates the achieved throughput in Mbps using the bit loading technique, compared to a fixed-size M-QAM scheme (where the same modulation is applied to every subcarrier) for a target BER of 10^{-5} in an AWGN channel. The results are provided for the required E_b/N_0 to achieve the target BER with the fixed-size M-QAM scheme. Fig. 2 presents the throughput results for a satellite uplink scenario using the NTN-TDLC5 channel model from 3GPP TS 38.101-5 Annex B [16] and a target BER of 10^{-4} . Significant throughput gains are observed in both cases, underscoring the importance of the adaptive technique in efficiently utilizing the spectrum in FM-OFDM.

C. Total Degradation (Figure of Merit)

In this subsection, we analyze the performance of FM-OFDM under the nonlinear effects of a HPA. We present a comparative study based on the TD for a range of OBO values. The TD was introduced [5], [6] to measure the BER performance degradation in the presence of a HPA, compared to the ideal AWGN channel, depending on its operating point, i.e., IBO or OBO, for a certain target BER. We define the IBO as the ratio between the power of the signal at the input of the HPA, and the input power saturating the amplifier [14]. The OBO is the equivalent measurement at the output of the HPA. The TD is given by

$$TD = \left(\frac{E_b}{N_0}\right)^{NL} - \left(\frac{E_b}{N_0}\right)^{AWGN} + OBO \text{ (dB)}, \quad (15)$$

Fig. 3. Total degradation as a measurement of BER performance degradation under the effects of a HPA.

where $\left(\frac{E_b}{N_0}\right)^{\text{AWGN}}$ is the required E_b/N_0 to achieve a target BER in an AWGN channel, and $\left(\frac{E_b}{N_0}\right)^{\text{NL}}$ is the E_b/N_0 to achieve the same BER considering the nonlinear effects of the HPA. In this work, we choose a target BER of 10^{-3} [7].

Fig. 3 shows the results for OFDM, DFT-spread-OFDM (DFT-s-OFDM), constant envelope OFDM (CE-OFDM) [10], OTFS [8] and FM-OFDM. The results demonstrate that FM-OFDM does not suffer from BER degradation in the presence of a HPA due to its constant envelope. While CE-OFDM shares this constant envelope advantage, it is not resilient to channel variations at high-mobility, as discussed in the next subsection. OTFS shows promise for high-mobility applications in future 6G systems, although its PAPR characteristics are similar to those of OFDM. A DFT-s-OTFS variant is also noted in the literature, but as shown in [17], its PAPR is comparable to that of DFT-s-OFDM.

D. NTN BER Performance Evaluation

This subsection presents the BER performance evaluation for both uplink and downlink scenarios described in subsection IV-A. For ease of comparison of the results with other waveforms, FM-OFDM is plotted using a fixed-size M-QAM modulation scheme. The gains achieved by employing the bit loading technique were detailed in subsection IV-B.

Fig. 4 illustrates the BER performance for the uplink scenario. This scenario considers the maximum residual frequency offset (CFO_{UL}^{max}), the NTN-TDLC5 channel model, and phase noise. FM-OFDM is compared with cyclic prefix-OFDM (CP-OFDM), DFT-s-OFDM, ZP-OFDM, and CE-OFDM.

CP-OFDM and DFT-s-OFDM are evaluated assuming perfect channel state information (CSI) with a single-tap frequency domain equalizer. These techniques saturate at high BERs primarily due to the significant Doppler shift, which leads to high ICI. This occurs even with perfect CSI and both pre and post compensation for common Doppler shift, due to the severe loss of orthogonality among subcarriers. Even the phase tracking-reference signals (PT-RS), which were specifically introduced by 3GPP to mitigate the effects of

phase noise, would be insufficient due to the presence of significant ICI.

ZP-OFDM is an OFDM variant that uses zero-padding instead of the cyclic prefix used in CP-OFDM. This allows for block equalization as proposed in [9], aiming to equalize a time-varying channel block-wise. However, ZP-OFDM remains susceptible to ICI and inter-block interference introduced during equalization, indicating that, although designed for time-varying channels, ZP-OFDM is not effective for extreme satellite scenarios at high frequencies as considered in this work.

CE-OFDM exhibits a marginal enhancement in performance relative to CP-OFDM, DFT-s-OFDM, and ZP-OFDM. This is due to the fact that phase impairments in CE-OFDM result in an additive noise term following the phase detector, whereas the other methods are more susceptible to phase noise [18]. Nevertheless, like CP-OFDM, CE-OFDM is unsuitable for high-mobility applications [10]. In contrast, FM-OFDM is well-suited for these scenarios due to the frequency modulator [4].

FM-OFDM is analyzed for both perfect CSI with block-equalization [9] and without CSI (no equalization). The performance difference between these two cases is negligible for low-order modulation schemes like QPSK and only slightly increases for 16-QAM. This indicates that channel estimation and equalization are not strictly necessary for FM-OFDM, thereby saving significant computational complexity. FM-OFDM demonstrates high robustness to Doppler shift and phase noise, making it a strong candidate waveform for NTN.

OTFS is a promising candidate for 6G waveforms, demonstrating performance comparable to FM-OFDM in some high-mobility scenarios [9]. OTFS is also robust against phase noise, though some mitigation technique may be necessary for a fair comparison. In this work, we compare FM-OFDM and OTFS in Fig. 5 for a downlink scenario, focusing on the effects of the HPA. The evaluation includes the residual

Fig. 4. Uplink BER performance: residual frequency offset after pre and post common Doppler shift compensation CFO_{UL}^{max} , NTN-TDLC5 channel model and phase noise.

Fig. 5. Downlink BER performance: Comparison between FM-OFDM and OTFS. Residual frequency offset due to satellite movement $CFO_{DL}^{max} \approx CFO_{UL}^{max}/2$, NTN-TDLC5 channel model and HPA nonlinearities.

frequency offset CFO_{DL}^{max} due to satellite speed, but excludes phase noise, assuming its mitigation in both cases in order to isolate the impact of high mobility and HPA effects on OTFS performance.

Results show that at low E_b/N_0 values, OTFS slightly outperforms FM-OFDM. However, it should be noted that perfect CSI is assumed for OTFS, making practical performance likely worse or comparable to FM-OFDM. At higher E_b/N_0 , OTFS BER saturates due to the HPA nonlinear effects, while FM-OFDM demonstrates superior performance without the need for channel estimation or equalization. In practice, OTFS also suffers from spectral efficiency loss due to pilot transmission, sensitivity to fractional Doppler shifts, and increased latency from the need to process multiple symbol blocks, further deteriorating OTFS performance. Channel coding could narrow the performance gap, but at the expense of reducing data rates. PAPR reduction techniques for OTFS or the DFT-s-OTFS [17] are being investigated, although they significantly increase the complexity. While OTFS is a strong candidate for some high-mobility scenarios, these results underscore the advantages of FM-OFDM in NTN environments.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This work proposes an adaptive FM-OFDM system to optimize the spectrum efficiency for this waveform, which inherently suffers from subcarrier SNR variations even in AWGN channels due to frequency modulation.

We also present a comparative study highlighting FM-OFDM's suitability for NTNs. We show that FM-OFDM is robust to high-mobility in a Ka band LEO satellite scenario, outperforming the 5G NR waveform CP-OFDM, which is highly sensitive to ICI due to Doppler shifts and phase noise. Additionally, FM-OFDM has a constant envelope that avoids the nonlinear distortions from HPAs, unlike CP-OFDM, which suffers from high PAPR. Furthermore, FM-OFDM does not require channel estimation or equalization under flat-frequency channels (LOS condition), which is the case for NTNs.

As 6G systems evolve towards more flexible and adaptive networks, the proposed adaptive FM-OFDM system, fully compatible with existing OFDM architectures, emerges as a promising candidate to support the complex demands of future 6G NTNs.

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